

COMPASS Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results Including Communication Activities

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Executive summary

This document is the “Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results Including Communication Activities” of the COMPASS project, aiming to ensure the coherent streamlining of the project outputs into targeted high-quality dissemination products, and their dissemination to specific target audiences.

Section 2 presents the pillars and the objectives of the COMPASS Dissemination and Communication (D&C) strategy, while Section 3 details the seven key target audience categories, namely: the scientific and research communities (particularly fields related to climate risks, climate attribution); the entrusted entities of the Copernicus services, SMEs, Consultants; the Civil Protection services; the stakeholders/ agencies involved in risk assessment of climate change attribution, climate attribution of compound extremes and/or analysis of the related societal impacts; the insurance companies; the policy community involved in the discussion on climate attribution, preparedness to extreme events, climate adaptation and mitigation; the general public.

The research and dissemination products to be developed expand in multiple broad directions and audiences:

- (i) the dissemination of the project results and scientific advances to the scientific and research community, the general ERA (European Research Area) and the RTD sector;
- (ii) the promotion of the foreground to the Copernicus entrusted entities and the business community for the development of operational climate services and downstream applications;
- (iii) the communication of specific project products to civil protection services to better inform their disaster reduction and emergency response planning;
- (iv) the interaction with stakeholders of the Use Cases for the integration of the project’s results (methods, tools, services) in their decision support systems;
- (v) the communication with insurance companies to enhance their understanding of compound extreme events and related risk analysis;
- (vi) the interfacing with policy in order to inform and support the EU policy needs, bridge relevant gaps, and improve preparedness;
- (vii) raising awareness of the general public

As such, the different dissemination and communication products and activities target a range of groups and will be tailored to their identified information needs. These are presented in detail in Section 4, along with a detailed time plan in Section 5.

The communication and dissemination processes will be closely monitored, and periodic evaluations will be held to assess the impact of the various activities and timely redesign (if deemed necessary) elements of the implemented approach which needs strengthening. A set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be used for this purpose as presented in Chapter 6. Finally, Chapter 7 discusses the dissemination products’ quality control and standards.

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1. Introduction

COMPASS “Compound extremes attribution of climate change: towards an operational service” is a collaborative project funded under the Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme. The project began in January 2024 and will run for 3 years.

The COMPASS project aims to develop a harmonised, yet flexible, methodological framework for climate and impact attribution of various hazard types, which is a crucial initial step towards the deployment of a European operational service. COMPASS will innovate by going from the attribution of single-driver extremes to the attribution of more complex extremes (including compounding, sequential and cascading hazard events) and enabling a shift from a hazard-centred analysis to an impact-centred perspective. Main novelties include event-based hazard and impact modelling using a multi-scale approach, the use of weather type analysis for better understanding the physical drivers that give rise compound extremes, and the use of contextualized storylines to communicate attribution results. Our framework will be validated and applied to a set of Use Cases that cover historical extremes for various hazard types and impact context, as well as extreme events happening during the project. These Use Cases (UCs) are an integral component of the project and are the vehicle for (i) collaboration and co-design of the models and workflows; (ii) validation of the methodological framework for real-world events that are well-described in literature; and (iii) showcasing the potential for an operational service that will attribute compound extremes to climate change.

The COMPASS products will be scalable for on-the fly analysis, transferable to other extremes and regions, and will lay the scientific foundation for the operational deployment as part of the Copernicus Climate Change Services. Dissemination and communication play thus an important role in the COMPASS project. For this purpose, a dedicated workpackage (WP7) has been specifically designed to allow the development of adequate mechanisms and tools to ensure the effective and targeted dissemination of all project results. Within its early tasks is the drafting of the current COMPASS Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of results including Communication activities (DCP), subject to review and update along the course of the project, in order to further strengthen the close cooperation among all the project work packages (WPs), to ensure the coherent streamlining of their findings and results into targeted and high-quality dissemination products, to pave the way from research to services’ implementation, to policy and decision-making, and to business development opportunities. The development of a Future Exploitation Plan (ExP) is also foreseen towards the end of the project, addressing more specifically potential exploitation and commercialization activities, further products, applications and services that can be built on the basis of the COMPASS outputs and integration into Copernicus services.

The different dissemination and communication products target a range of audiences: (1) the scientific and research communities (particularly fields related to climate risks, climate attribution); (2) the entrusted entities of the Copernicus services, SMEs, Consultants; (3) the Civil Protection services; (4) the stakeholders/ agencies involved in risk assessment of climate change attribution, climate attribution of compound extremes and/or analysis of the related societal impacts; (5) the insurance companies; (6) the policy community involved in the discussion on climate attribution, preparedness to extreme events, climate adaptation and mitigation; (7) the general public.

This document is the first version of the “Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results Including Communication Activities” of the COMPASS project. The Plan will be regularly updated during the course of the project, as feedback from the monitoring and evaluation of the

dissemination activities is collected, and should refinement or re-design of specific elements is required to strengthen the impact of dissemination.

2. The Dissemination and Communication Strategy

COMPASS represents one of the first attempts to attribute the occurrence and impacts of compound extremes to climate change and climate variability. Using concepts from climate/earth sciences, engineering, risk management and social science, COMPASS will develop a basis for a practical application in an operational setting and its evolution into a new Copernicus Climate Change core service. Such a service would on the one hand raise awareness of the impacts of climate change at various policy levels (local, regional, national, and global) and, on the other hand, provide crucial information that support better planning and decision-making. The significance of COMPASS impact is thus high. Furthermore, the acquired knowledge and technology in COMPASS can contribute to the urgent need to provide insights and awareness on the impacts of climate change in the global debate on climate adaptation and mitigation, and ultimately make European regions more climate-resilient supporting the design of improved policy and action plans. To maximise the project impact, the COMPASS Dissemination and Communication Strategy is based on four main pillars:

1. **raising awareness** on the impact of climate extremes and compound events,
2. **reaching the right audience** to promote the use and uptake of the COMPASS results, services and tools,
3. **providing guidance and capacity building** for climate attribution, analysis of compound events, etc.,
4. **advocating and promoting recommendations** on strengthening EU related policies and developing an operational service as part of the Copernicus Climate Change Services

The Dissemination and Communication Strategy components include:

- Definition of dissemination and communication (D&C) objectives
- Identification of the targeted audiences and the specific objectives for each audience
- Development of the D&C activities, mechanisms and tools
- Monitoring and evaluation of the impact of the D&C activities

Figure 1: Components of the COMPASS dissemination and communication strategy

2.1. Objectives of the Dissemination and Communication Strategy

The COMPASS C&D strategy objectives have been defined with the goal to maximise the project impact, ensuring that relevant information and key outputs of the project are relayed to the suitable target audience via the most appropriate channels. The objectives of the C&D Strategy are:

1. Produce quality-assured dissemination products and ensure timely distribution to the different target audiences.
2. Exploit the full potentiality of dissemination media (social media, networks, etc.).
3. Develop and use innovative tools which facilitate diffusion of the results and further support stakeholders' interaction and exchange (tailored to the end-users).
4. Build capacity of targeted groups, develop a Community of Practice (CoP), networks and EU-wide alliances, and maximize the involvement of citizens, end-users and stakeholders in water management.
5. Design and implement educational activities.
6. Link research and innovation to the regional and EU policy.
7. Develop an Exploitation Plan (including IPR) addressing the uptake and commercialization of the foreground.

2.2. Specific goals for the Use Cases' stakeholders

The COMPASS methods and modelling framework for compound extremes will be validated and applied to a set of diverse Use Cases (UCs), which cover compound events, sequences of events and cascading events, and will be co-developed from the collaboration between physical, societal and

practice-oriented experts. The Use Cases are an integral component of the project. They are the vehicle for: (1) collaboration and co-design of the models and workflows with stakeholders; (2) validation of the methodological framework for real-world events that are well-described in literature; and (3) showcasing the potential for an operational service that will attribute compound extremes to climate change. Some of the UCs focus on a single sequential or compound event in detail, while other UCs focus on different types of compound events in the same region. Five Use Cases have already been identified (as presented in the Table below), while a second set of additional Use Cases will be selected during the project. This flexibility will allow investigating most recent extreme events that have societal relevance, as well as testing the transferability of the developed modelling approaches and attribution methods other events and regions.

COMPASS will actively engage with relevant stakeholders in the Use Cases (such as NGOs, local governments, Copernicus) to help define relevant impact-pathways, storylines of future vulnerability and exposure, and disseminate results. By involving local stakeholders in a co-creation process, we aim to increase our impact on the Use Cases and boost uptake of results. Thus, the stakeholder communities of the Use Cases will be given a special attention when it comes to communication, dissemination and capacity building, with escalating specific goals (depending on the different user interests in each Use Case), starting from increasing the awareness (push-communication), to gaining their acceptance (pull-communication), to engagement in co-development, to uptake of the COMPASS framework and tools, and finally to mainstreaming of the tools as part of an operational climate service.

Table 1: Overview of the use cases (UCs)

UC	Region	Type extreme	Compound extreme event – type of hazard	
1	France	Compound	Storm Xynthia (Winter 2010) - coastal flood and windstorm	
2	United Kingdom	Compound and sequential/compound	Clustering of winter storms (2013/14) - compound flooding, wind, rain	Compounding heatwave (2022) - high temperature, drought, and wildfires
3	Eastern Africa	Compound and sequential/compound	Tropical Cyclone Idai and Kenneth (2019), Tropical Cyclone Freddy (2023) - compound flooding, rainfall, wind	Drought and saltwater intrusion (2015/16)
4	Caribbean	Sequential event	Tropical Cyclones Eta and Iota (2014)	
5	Poland	Compound	Drought and heatwaves for a single-country, no specific event, but ran operationally	

Figure 2: Levels of Use Case stakeholders' engagement in the co-development and uptake of the COMPASS products and tools

3. The Target Audience

Given the nature of the COMPASS project, cutting across the scientific themes of climate and impact attribution and risk assessment, there is a variety of interesting topics to be communicated. The research and dissemination products to be developed expand in multiple broad directions and audiences:

- (i) the dissemination of the project results and scientific advances to the scientific and research community, the general ERA (European Research Area) and the RTD sector;
- (ii) the promotion of the foreground to the Copernicus entrusted entities and the business community for the development of operational climate services and downstream applications;
- (iii) the communication of specific project products to civil protection services to better inform their disaster reduction and emergency response planning;
- (iv) the interaction with stakeholders of the Use Cases for the integration of the project's results (methods, tools, services) in their decision support systems;

- (v) the communication with insurance companies to enhance their understanding of compound extreme events and related risk analysis;
- (vi) the interfacing with policy in order to inform and support the EU policy needs, bridge relevant gaps, and improve preparedness;
- (vii) raising awareness of the general public

As such, the different dissemination and communication products will be targeted to a range of groups and will be tailored to their identified information needs.

Figure 3: Dissemination and communication target audience

Dissemination and communication will assess the information needs of the target groups (as presented in the following sections (i.e. scientific, policy and business communities, etc.)), including when the information is most needed and is likely to serve as an “agent of change”. When planning for a dissemination activity, the COMPASS team will be aware when a window of opportunity arises (e.g. scientific conference, high-level policy forum, specific event, etc.) and make the information available in a manner that is appropriate for the technical and functional needs of the target audience.

The following target audiences A1-A7 have been defined, along with specific D&C objectives per audience, as presented in the Table below. The dissemination of the COMPASS results will be targeting these groups, using messages linked to their values, interests and motivations to ensure knowledge transfer and uptake of the services and tools developed.

Table 2: Dissemination and communication target audiences and relevant objectives per audience

Who to reach?	Why?
A1: Scientific and research communities (particularly fields related to climate risks, climate attribution)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To enhance the use of the COMPASS datasets, methods, modelling frameworks on climate and impact attribution of compound events by scientists for their work and further research. • To develop a Community of Practice and build capacity
A2: Entrusted Entities of the Copernicus services, SMEs, Consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To capitalize the project foreground for developing new business and operational services, including Copernicus Climate Change service, and providing better support to end-users and clients
A3: Civil Protection Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To promote and support the integration of project components/ products into their disaster reduction cycle and improve emergency response
A4: Stakeholders/ agencies involved in risk assessment of climate change attribution, climate attribution of compound extremes and/or analysis of the related societal impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To shift towards multi-hazard assessments instead of continuing working in silos which has often resulted in an underestimation of the impacts of extreme events • To better understand and get prepared for the impacts of (future) extremes
A5: Insurance companies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To enhance the understanding of climate attribution of compound extreme events and related risk analysis • To facilitate the conduction of fit-for-purpose risk assessments
A6: Policy community involved in the discussion on climate attribution, preparedness to extreme events, climate adaptation and mitigation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To communicate the need to be prepared for compound extreme events, and support its mainstreaming into policy actions. • To support the design of climate adaptation measures accounting for the impacts of compound events and the underlying vulnerability factors
A7: The general public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General awareness raising

It is acknowledged that the different above-mentioned target audiences have different levels of interest and influence/relevance related to the COMPASS products, tools and services. The dissemination and communication efforts will be thus targeted and optimised accordingly, with basic information for awareness raising provided in the “low influence, low interest” audiences, to detailed information and capacity development provided in the “high influence, high interest” audience in order to boost uptake, mainstreaming and capitalisation of the COMPASS foreground. The groups A1, A2, A4 have been identified as Category 4 “high influence, high interest” and will be thus prioritised.

Figure 4: Dissemination and communication efforts based on the identified target audiences influence and interest

3.1. Scientific and research community (A1)

One of the main target groups of the COMPASS dissemination activities is the European Research Area (ERA) and the wider global research community involved in the study of natural hazards, climate attributions and disaster risk. Given the context of the COMPASS project, the A1 target audience is a priority audience, and the fact that the project itself involves many research partners, each one of them having established networks, will secure the selection of the proper scientific groups to address. The research community will be sensitised on the project activities through the transnational dissemination events, the organization of conference sessions and events dedicated to specific scientific issues of the project (e.g. hazard modelling and climate attribution, impact modelling of compound events, vulnerability analysis, etc.), the various targeted publications in journals, the developed webinars and e-learning material. We will also reach out to young professionals as a special group. Below, we provide a list of indicative scientific projects and initiatives of relevance to the COMPASS that we will be networking with and disseminating the COMPASS scientific advances.

Table 3: List of indicative scientific projects and initiatives of relevance to the COMPASS dissemination of the research foreground and scientific networking

Acronym	Title
Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) and related Demonstrator Projects	Operational service for the water sector of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) C3S projects to provide European/global projections of extreme sea level, including use cases on flood risk management, offshore wind, etc.
C3S - Sectoral applications of	Sectoral applications of decadal predictions for: agriculture, energy,

decadal predictions	infrastructure, insurance
CLIMAAX	Development of a climate risk assessment framework and toolbox to be applied by European 50 regions
ISIMIP	The Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (hosted at PIK, strong synergies with COMPASS)
CASCADES	H2020 project on the impacts of cascading climate hazards in Europe
XAIDA	“eXtreme events : Artificial Intelligence for Detection and Attribution” is a Horizon Europe project developing new methods for understanding how climate change modifies and enhances extreme weather events
TRANSCEND	Transformational and robust adaptation to water scarcity and climate change under deep uncertainty
EUPHEME	ERA4CS project developing a scientific platform and new methods to attribute the risks of extreme events to human and natural causes
Climateurope2	Supporting and standardizing climate services in Europe and beyond
ClimXtreme	A research network on climate change and extreme events
RiskKAN	A knowledge action network on emergent risks and extreme events
Destination Earth	DestinE Digital Twin Use Cases focus on compound flooding, focussing on five use cases on disaster risk reduction and climate adaptation
REACHOUT	Resilience in Europe through activating city hubs reaching out to users with triple-a climate adaptation tools
TACTIC	Tools for Assessment of Climate change Impact on Groundwater and Adaptation Strategies
WMO HydroSOS initiative	Global Hydrological Status and Outlook System (HydroSOS)
JPI Climate	Joint Programming Initiative "Connecting Climate Knowledge for Europe"
MuSe-BDA	Multi-Sensor Bayesian Data Assimilation for Large-Scale Drought Monitoring System
TEMBO Africa	Transformative Environmental Monitoring to Boost Observations in Africa
MAGDA	Meteorological assimilation for accurate weather forecasting and efficient irrigation
AGILE	A European research project aiming to combine and integrate a wide range of established and innovative methodologies into a novel and replicable multi-sectoral risk and resilience stress testing methodology.
EO4Multihazards	“Earth Observation for High-Impact Multi-Hazards Science” is an ESA project, aiming to use state-of-the-art satellite Earth Observation to improve the understanding of high-impact cascading and compounding multi-hazard events
RETURN	“Multi-risk science for resilient communities under a changing climate” aims to to enforce the key competences, the technological and knowledge transfer, and to strengthen Italian governance in managing disaster risk
MYRIAD-EU	Horizon 2020 project aiming to develop a harmonised framework for multi-hazard, multi-sector, and systemic risk management
MEDiate	A Horizon Europe project aiming to develop a decision support system for disaster risk management for multi-hazard, compound and cascading events that accounts for changes in hazard, exposure and vulnerability

PARATUS	“Promoting disaster preparedness and resilience by co-developing stakeholder support tools for managing the systemic risk of compounding disasters” is a Horizon project that will perform in-depth assessments of complex interactions between hazards and their resulting impacts in various sectors, as well as analyse the current risk situation and study how alternative future scenarios could change multi-hazard impact chains
The HuT	The Human-Tech Nexus - Building a Safe Haven to cope with Climate Extremes. A Horizon project aiming to promote a set of trans-disciplinary risk management tools and approaches that could be adopted and used in as many situations as possible
C2IMPRESS	A Horizon Europe project aiming to increase awareness of multi-hazard risks and improve the prediction of future extreme weather events through the development of operational system dynamic models.
PARATUS	A Horizon project performing in-depth assessments of historical multi-hazard events and how future scenarios could change the impacts observed to improve preparedness of first and second responders
BORIS/BORIS 2	“Cross BOrder RISk assessment for increased prevention and preparedness in Europe: way forward”, funded by DG-ECHO, aims to deliver a methodology and tool to support stakeholders to undertake strategic decisions to improve emergency planning
CoCLiCo	A Horizon 2020 project to develop an open web platform to help inform decision making on coastal risk and highlight risk drivers
MIRACA	“Multi-hazard Infrastructure Risk Assessment for Climate Adaptation” is a Horizon project aiming to develop a research-based toolkit that promotes adaptation measures which prepare Europe’s critical infrastructure to withstand extreme weather events
DIRECTED	A Horizon project aiming to reduce vulnerability to extreme weather events and foster disaster-resilient European societies, by promoting interoperability of data, models, communication and governance on all levels and between all actors of the disaster risk management and climate adaptation process
MedCyclones	European network for Mediterranean cyclones in weather and climate (COST actions with 29 participating countries)
FloodDrivers	“Decomposition of flood losses by environmental and economic drivers” project on flood impact attribution
SPARCCLE	Horizon Europe project that is co-developing modelling tools with policymakers, scientists and civil society to support us all in making better decisions to reduce the risks and build resilience within the society and economy of Europe in the face of climate change.
Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change (CMCC)	CMCC mission is to investigate and model our climate system and its interactions with society to provide reliable, rigorous, and timely scientific results to stimulate sustainable growth, protect the environment and develop science driven adaptation and mitigation policies in a changing climate
Climate Alliance	Climate Alliance (European city network dedicated to climate action)
Climate-KIC	EIT Climate-KIC is a leading climate innovation agency and community, supporting cities, regions, countries and industries to meet their climate ambitions through systems innovation and place-based transformations

EU Joint Research Center (JRC)	EU JRC (coordinated research activity on climate and impact attribution of a large ensemble of past extreme events in EU)
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3.2. Entrusted Entities of the Copernicus services, SMEs, Consultants (A2)

This target audience is a priority audience for COMPASS, falling under the category 4 “high influence, high interest” since they can directly uptake and exploit the project foreground into further developing operational climate services and downstream applications. A2 includes:

- Entrusted Entities of the Copernicus services, e.g. the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)
- SMEs and Start-ups (e.g. participants of the Copernicus Start-up Programme, the Copernicus Relays Networks, etc.), Consultants, Practitioners involved in: water resources modelling applications, climate change assessments, floods and droughts prediction and forecasting, water resources management, Earth Observation data applications, data assimilation and/or monitoring, science-policy interfacing and applications for operational decision making/decision support systems’ development

Among the project’s goals is to evaluate opportunities arising for new operational services and business matching the COMPASS products with innovative ideas, which will be investigated and addressed through a dedicated Future Exploitation Plan (ExP).

3.3. Civil Protection Services (A3)

Civil protection services can benefit from the integration of specific COMPASS products and components into their disaster reduction cycle and improve emergency response. This target audience will receive tailored materials focusing on risk management. The following networks of professionals and practitioners have also been identified for networking and dissemination purposes on disaster risk management topics:

[CMINE](#) : A hub for crisis management professionals in the EU and beyond. It aims to foster innovation and research uptake in crisis management through cross-sector, multi-stakeholder dialogues around capability gaps and potential solutions

[KI-CoP](#) : Network of practitioners put forward from the European project ENGAGE, aiming to improve disaster risk management through citizen engagement and awareness

3.4. Stakeholders/ agencies involved in climate analysis, climate attribution, risk assessment, analysis of societal impacts (A4)

This target audience includes a range of stakeholders involved in risk assessment of climate change attribution, climate attribution of compound extremes and/or analysis of the related societal impacts. The COMPASS communication and dissemination activities will promote a shift towards multi-hazard assessments instead of continuing working in silos (which has often resulted in an underestimation of the impacts of extreme events), and will also enhance the understanding of how to better prepare for future extremes. This audience also includes the local stakeholders on the Use

Cases. As already mentioned previously (see section 2.2) COMPASS will pursue the active engagement of the Use Cases' stakeholders in a co-creation process (i.e. help define relevant impact-pathways, storylines of future vulnerability and exposure) in order to increase the project impact on the Use Cases and boost uptake of results.

Indicative stakeholders and agencies in this target audience include:

- Local Stakeholders: local, regional or national stakeholders involved in climate attribution and/or risk management in the fields of water resources, agricultural, forest, spatial planning or environmental protection (whoever applicable in a particular country)
- National Meteorological Offices
- European Climate Adaptation Platform Climate-ADAPT (a partnership between the European Commission and the European Environment Agency)
- European Topic Centre on Climate Change Impacts, Vulnerability and Adaptation (ETC/CCA)
- International Conventions (e.g. ICPDR, ICPR)

3.5. Insurance Companies (A5)

Insurance companies can benefit from the COMPASS outputs to enhance their understanding of climate attribution of compound extreme events and related risk analysis, and to further conduct fit-for-purpose risk assessments. This target audience will receive tailored materials focusing on exposure and vulnerability aspects, risk analysis and impact attribution. Munich Re, Swiss Re and AXA are examples of relevant insurance companies that would be interested by the outputs and methodology from the project.

3.6. Policy community involved in the discussion on climate attribution, preparedness to extreme events, climate adaptation and mitigation (A6)

Among the COMPASS objectives is to raise awareness and improve preparedness for climate change impacts at various policy levels, and support more accurate decision-making, policy risk reduction and response. It is thus clear that the policy community can benefit from the COMPASS project findings and experience and is in this sense a valuable end-user and target audience. An impact attribution service is only useful if it is relevant to society, and therefore it is important to clearly communicate the findings of the attribution studies and link science-to-policy. Policy-makers can benefit from targeted "attribution briefs" that describe the event and the impact, and recommendations to increase the resilience to this type of events. The knowledge and technology in COMPASS can provide insights and awareness on the impacts of climate change in the global debate on climate adaptation and mitigation and ultimately make European regions more climate resilient supporting the design of improved policy and action plans. The Use Cases can form the basis for a science-policy dialogue to share the attribution findings and discuss their relevance for informing policies and planning around adaptation, loss and damage, or disaster recovery. The fact that the projects involve partners active in the science-policy interfacing processes, each one of them having established networks, will secure the selection of the proper policy audience to address. The following entities and actors have been identified:

- High-level Policy stakeholders
 - National governments (ministries), local and regional governments (whoever appropriate in a particular country)

- European Commission (e.g. DG Environment, DG Climate, DG Agriculture, DG Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations, DG Regional Policy, HADEA, CINEA)
 - Common Implementation Strategy Working Groups (CIS WFD, CIS Floods, EG Water Scarcity & Drought, etc.)
 - UN Office for Disaster Risk Reduction, UNDRR
 - United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC)
- Environmental agencies and non-governmental organisations and networks
 - European Environment Agency (EEA)
 - European Environment Information and Observation Network (EIONET)
 - Copernicus, Group on Earth Observation (GEO)
 - WMO Water and Climate Coalition
 - UNESCO-IHP
 - World's Large Rivers Initiative
 - High Level Experts and Leaders Panel on Water and Disasters (HELP)
 - Water and Climate Coalition
 - Global Adaptation Centre
 - UNESCO World Water Assessment Programme (WWAP)
 - Alliance for Global Water Adaptation (AGWA)
 - International environmental organisations (e.g. WWF, IUCN, Wetlands International)

3.7. General public (A5)

Reaching out to general public will be pursued within the project. COMPASS communications will follow unified central messaging, but with respect to also adapting to the general public communication channels and styles. Essential messages will be thus tailored to the general public and the civil society organisations to allow for easy understanding and awareness raising. The messages will be disseminated through the COMPASS website, social media, and citizens-oriented informational material.

4. Dissemination and Communication Activities, Mechanisms & Tools

The COMPASS communication and dissemination activities, and related material, follow the well-known principle 5W1H (Who, What, Why, When, Where and How), aiming to provide tailored communication products to all identified target audiences. The different dissemination and communication activities, mechanisms tools to be deployed are analytically described in the following sections and summarized in Table 4. Targeted mechanisms will be mobilized and the activities will be implemented in a stepwise process in order to achieve the objectives of the dissemination strategy, subject to review and updating along the course of the project to maintain a dynamic process, and maximize the intended impact. All dissemination products will acknowledge the funding received by the EU Commission and will follow the publicity rules set by Horizon, and will be compliant with the relevant dissemination rules and guidelines.

Table 4: Overview of the D&C activities, mechanisms and tools, and their relevance per target audience

D&C Activities, Mechanisms and Tools	Target Audience						
	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7
Portfolio of dissemination products addressed to all audiences/communities							
COMPASS website	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Social media pages	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
General promotional/informational material (leaflets, brochures, presentations, posters, articles)	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
E-Newsletters	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
COMPASS Final Conference	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Dissemination to the Scientific and Research Community							
Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals	√	√	√	√			
Presentations/posters in international conferences	√	√	√	√	√	√	
Open access data	√	√	√	√	√	√	
Online demonstrator of the use cases	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Outreach, interaction and capacity building							
Workshops with Use Cases' local stakeholders				√			
Training activities (webinars)	√	√	√	√	√		
Guidance document for operational deployment	√	√	√	√	√		
Hackathon for early career scientists	√						
Information day linked to operational deployment and new services		√	√	√	√		
Webinar for policy makers				√		√	
Networking with relevant initiatives	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Linking Science and Innovation to the Decision and Policy-Making function							
Attribution Briefs		√	√	√	√	√	√
Layman's Report		√	√	√	√	√	√
Future exploitation and sustainability							
Customized communication material		√	√	√	√		
COMPASS Future Exploitation Plan (ExP)	√	√	√	√	√	√	√

4.1. D&C-4-all: Portfolio of dissemination products and tools addressed to all audiences/communities

A wide range of web-based and printed dissemination products and tools will be developed to support the timely and up-to-date diffusion of information and improved communication addressed to all target audiences/ communities, as presented below:

- COMPASS website (www.compass-climate.eu): to be maintained for 5 more years after the project ends, and used to disseminate updates on activities, deliverables, interesting news/posts, events, etc. A search engine optimisation (SEO) strategy will be implemented in order to increase the outreach.
- A LinkedIn COMPASS Group (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/9816085/>), where targeted audience will be invited to join.
- General promotional/informational material (leaflets, brochures, presentations, posters, articles). The main presentations and brochures will be translated into several languages (including all the languages of the Use Cases) to reach a wider audience. Relevant existing online dissemination platforms will also be reached.
- E-Newsletters (every 6 months) updating on the progress and disseminating news.
- The COMPASS Final Conference, attached to a main event to maximise impact.

The COMPASS Project Website (www.compass-climate.eu) will play an important role in a two-way communication with interested stakeholders. It will be used for presenting the project description and deliverables, informing on the project activities and outputs, publicizing interesting posts and events. All the public results will be posted and available on this site. A dedicated section for the media is visible and easily accessible containing brief articles, newsletters, alerts on upcoming events and regular news posts on climate attribution, extreme events (e.g. floods, tropical cyclones, heatwaves, etc.), compound extremes, climate change impacts, etc. In more detail, the COMPASS website is envisioned to be active and dynamic and contains the following sections:

- HOME: This page is the homepage/landing of the project, containing direct links to all the other tabs, displaying some general info on the project, and selected news and events. The home page follows the COMPASS corporate design.
- PROJECT: This section provides detailed information on the project, its objectives, the state-of-the-art and policy context, as well as an overview of the workplan and work packages and their interconnection.
- USE CASES: This section provides the basic information for each use case. Each use case has, for that purpose, a dedicated webpage, which will evolve as new information and products are available through the project (climate attribution analysis, climate risk assessment, data, etc.). The use cases pages are planned to be updated when new information is obtained or produced.
- PARTNERS: This section introduces the project partners, and provides some basic info/facts on each partner.
- OUTPUT: This section is dedicated to downloaded material made available by the project, under 5 main categories: public deliverables, project presentation, publications, data, code.
- TRAININGS: This section will be built up as an open source Learning Management System and will host training courses, which include live webinars (online training workshops) or recorded e-learning sessions (webinars) accessible for users at any time.

- NEWS: This section is dedicated to brief articles, newsletters, posts on related topics, etc. This information is screened and selected by the partners with the goal to being up-to-date and serving as an important trigger to the readers
- EVENTS: This section is used to inform the public on interesting upcoming events. The events are listed in chronological order, while the past events are kept in archive.
- CONTACT: This section is the entry point to allow for contacting the project team. Emails are possible using a predefined format with “subject” options to allow the quick allocation of the enquiries among the partners. The General Data Protection Regulation is taken into consideration.

4.2. D&C-4-science: Dissemination to the Scientific and Research Community

As an R&I project COMPASS will produce important outputs marking its contributions to science in the ERA and beyond. Dissemination products and activities foreseen:

- Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals: Open access (gold and green) papers, complying with the strategy of the EC. Also a Special COMPASS Issue in a scientific journal
- Presentations/posters and sessions in international conferences (e.g. EGU, AGU, WRCP, ECCA, WMO), and the COMPASS Final Conference.
- Open Access Data: new data and methods (from WPs 1, 2, 3) will be made available through open-access online data sharing repositories (e.g. Zenodo, MetOffice Weather Data Hub, Figshare, C3S Climate Data Store) in line with the existing IPR.
- Online Demonstrator presenting the results of the Use Cases.

4.3. D&C-4-capacity: Outreach and capacity building

The outreach and capacity building is a central goal of the COMPASS dissemination, closely related to the COMPASS WP3, WP4 and WP5, and is dedicated to pursuing end-users’ engagement and capacity development. The objective is twofold: (a) interact on one hand with the competent authorities and collect input and feedback (co-development process); (b) build capacity of the end-users by providing tailored training and building a Community of Practice (CoP) that can uptake and further exploit the COMPASS products and services. Gender equal participation will be pursued in all our capacity building activities. Activities foreseen:

- Workshops with local stakeholders: Participatory workshops in the Uses Cases with local community stakeholders in order to: (a) co-develop contextualised storylines for each case study (within WP4/task 4.2) and fortify co-creation; (b) enhance the uptake and use of the COMPASS products and services, e.g. implementation of automated workflow solution for climate attribution
- Training activities: COMPASS Training Material will be built up as an open source Learning Management System and will address different user communities with different courses. Training courses will include live online training workshops or recorded e-learning sessions (webinars) accessible for users at any time, on different WPs’ products (e.g. on the task 5.1 automated workflow and related Jupyter Notebooks). The selected content of developed courses will remain accessible after the project by the partners.
- Guidance document for operational deployment: we will develop a guideline document that synthesises the results from the project and describes the methodological steps to attribute

compound extremes to climate change and natural variability. This includes the compilation of a protocol that describes the steps of a standardised approach in detail. The document will provide practical guidelines and procedures for applying the COMPASS methodological framework in practice.

- Hackathon: linked to GEOSS/HACK, this will be a social coding event for 25-50 early career scientists to implement the COMPASS framework (D1.2) to any event by running the automated workflow solution (D5.2) and/or implementing outputs of WP2, WP3 for capacity building and testing of the COMPASS approach.
- An information day to enhance transferring of the project results to operational deployment and generate business and new services (including civil protection services).
- A dedicated webinar to inform policy makers at the national and EU level about the need to consider compound events and climate attributions in climate risk assessment and related decision-making.
- Networking with relevant local initiatives and stakeholders, entrusted entities of the Copernicus services, civil protection services, insurance companies and the wider climate community.

4.4. D&C-4-policy: Linking Science and Innovation to the Decision and Policy-Making function

Specific science-policy interfacing activities are foreseen, aiming at facilitating the science-policy dialogues and the transfer of the COMPASS outputs into the decision-making field. The target audience includes high-level policy-makers and decision-makers within the key affiliated economic sectors, environmental agencies, civil protection services, humanitarian organisations, non-governmental organisations and networks. As these actors support different elements of the policy cycles and economic development decisions, and at different levels of the value chain, a prioritization will be made as to the most relevant for COMPASS. The foreseen dissemination products and activities include:

- Attribution briefs: an impact attribution service is only useful if it is relevant to society, and therefore it is important to clearly communicate the findings of the attribution studies. Therefore, we will communicate the findings of the Use Case in a series of “Attribution briefs” that will be tailored to specific audiences (such as national/local policy makers, civil protection services, insurance companies, humanitarian organisations, companies, or urban planners depending on the Use Case).
- Science-policy Dialogue: A subset of the Use Cases will form the basis for a science-policy dialogue to share the attribution findings and discuss their relevance for informing policies and planning around adaptation, loss and damage, or disaster recovery.
- Layman’s Report (~50 pp., precise, addressed to a non-technical audience).

4.5. D&C-4-business: Future exploitation and sustainability

A set of exploitation activities are foreseen in order to identify and pursue opportunities for the exploitation of the project foreground, opting the uptake of the project outcome as a Copernicus service, the uptake of the outputs by the business community (SMEs, consultants, young professionals, etc.) and the civil protection services, the matching with innovative ideas that can help SMEs to further develop services and products, and the increased involvement of the practitioners and stakeholders

Special emphasis will be placed on promoting gender equality within the communication strategy, and more particularly empowering women. The planned activities include:

- Customised communication material for the wider business and climate services community
- COMPASS Future Exploitation Plan (ExP): The ExP will draft a strategy for the follow-up of the project and its integration into Copernicus services. It will identify potential exploitation and commercialization activities, as well as further products, applications and services that can be built on the basis of the COMPASS outputs. Among the issues investigated in the ExP will be the development of a Community of Practice (CoP) to strengthen the sustainability of the capacity building, and the further use and capitalisation of the developed training activities after the project including the design of a training-of-trainers (ToT) roadmap.

5. Detailed Plan: timing and responsibilities

5.1. Timeplan of the dissemination and communication activities

The timeplan of the dissemination and communication activities is presented in Table 5.

5.2. Database of end-users and recipients

To organize the data concerning the recipients of the COMPASS communication and dissemination products a Database of dissemination recipients/groups will be developed, including the relevant networks to link to, taking into consideration the General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation EU 2016/679¹) and the our privacy policy. This database will include people who have contacted us via the social media, or who have directly subscribed in our newsletter/communication list via the COMPASS website. This will secure the easy communication as information will be properly classified, as well as the establishment of selected groups upon request (based on specific context). Relevant electronic mailing lists will be also created to facilitate the communication, e.g.: Stakeholders' list (all stakeholders, grouped by categories if necessary); Entities-SMEs' list (all SMEs contacts); Civil Protection list, etc.

¹ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

6. Monitoring and Evaluation

6.1. Monitoring and feedback on the activities

The communication and dissemination processes will be closely monitored, and periodic evaluations will be held to assess the impact of the various activities and timely redesign (if deemed necessary) elements of the implemented approach which needs strengthening.

A feedback and learning mechanism for the effectiveness of the dissemination strategy and quality of the particular knowledge product(s) will be established. These surveys will be made available to the target audience, and will be collected upon specific occasions (e.g. during conferences and events, after the distributions of e-newsletters, after webinars, etc.). When analysing the feedback, different questions will be asked, such as: To what extent has the COMPASS dissemination information been useful (in the broader sense and/or for guiding a specific process)? Has the information been made available in a timely manner to effectively influence decision-making processes? Have the products reached both direct and indirect audiences in an efficient manner and were they easily accessible? Did the audience find the knowledge products useful? If not, why not? What could be done better next time? Was the communication clear and well structured?, etc. Lessons from this feedback loop will be reflected and used to strengthen the antecedent dissemination efforts so that the information distributed to the various audiences is relevant and contributes to the learning and the enhancement of the global knowledge.

Within the consortium, and for keeping good track of all the activities a high level of internal information exchange will be established, where partners will report on their communication and publicity activities to the appointed Dissemination Officer, based on a pre-defined template, who will gather, merge and transfer these reports to the Project Coordinator. A Google form has been developed for this purpose.

COMPOUND EXTREMES ATTRIBUTION OF CLIMATE CHANGE: TOWARDS AN OPERATIONAL SERVICE

Template for reporting the dissemination and communication activities

<p>Type of activities <i>Please select from the drop-down list. In case the drop-down list in the next cell is not working, refer to the list at the end of this document (see Table 1), and type it in manually</i></p>	<p>Choose an item. Choose an item from the drop-down list Webpage Social media page Leaflet / brochure / flyer Scientific Publication General publication Organisation of Workshop/ Event Organisation of Webinar Organisation of Conference/ side session Presentation in a scientific event / conference Presentation in Workshop / Event Poster Exhibition Articles published in the popular press Oral presentation to a wider public Media briefing Press release Video Interview Thesis Documentary/ Film TV clip</p>	<p>or...type in manually from Table 1</p>
Name of partner leading the activity		
Other partners involved in this activity		
Title of the activity (or title of the publication)		
Title of the event (if applicable) e.g. title of Conference		
Location of the event (if applicable) e.g. Conference venue		
Date (dd/mm/yyyy)		
Type of target audience (please mark with X) <i>For a detailed description of the Target Audience please see Table 2 below</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> A1: Scientific and research communities <input type="checkbox"/> A2: Entrusted Entities of the Copernicus services, SMEs, Consultants <input type="checkbox"/> A3: Civil Protection Services <input type="checkbox"/> A4: Stakeholders/ agencies involved in risk assessment of climate change attribution, climate attribution of compound extremes and/or analysis of the related societal impacts <input type="checkbox"/> A5: Insurance companies <input type="checkbox"/> A6: Policy community involved in the discussion on climate attribution, preparedness to extreme events, climate adaptation and mitigation <input type="checkbox"/> A7: General public	
Size of audience		
Countries addressed		
Brief Description of the activity		

Figure 5: Template for reporting the dissemination and communication activities

6.2. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

For the evaluation of the dissemination and communication activities a set of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be used as presented in the Table below.

Table 6: Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the dissemination and communication activities plan

Dissemination and Communication activities	KPIs
COMPASS Website	> 5,000 visitors > 20,000 Pageviews
Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube)	> 60 followers > 30 post
General promotional/ informational material, E-newsletters	> 200 recipients > 5 E-newsletters
Scientific publications in peer-reviewed journals Presentations/posters in international conferences	>10 high-quality articles in peer-review journals >15 presentations in conferences >1 special issue in a high-quality journal 1 special conference session
New data and methods available online on open-access data sharing repositories	Open-access COMPASS data available in at least 1 repository
Online web-based demonstrator	1 online demonstrator > 100 visitors
Guidance document for operational deployment	1 Guidance document > 100 recipients
Training activities/ online webinars	> 3 Webinars > 100 participants
COMPASS Hackathon	25-50 early career scientist's participation
Policy Briefs	Minimum 2 Policy Briefs >40 recipients
Layman's Report	1 Layman Report > 300 recipients
Participatory Workshops with local stakeholders	Minimum 3 Workshops > 30 participants
Dedicated Policy webinar	1 policy webinar > 30 participants
The COMPASS Final Conference	1 Final Conference > 60 participants
Information Day	1 Information Day > 25 participants
Future Exploitation Plan (Exp)	1 Exp > 60 recipients

Besides the monitoring and evaluation of dissemination and communication activities a special effort will be put into evaluation of the overall project impact. Within the last quarter of the project, the selected COMPASS target audiences will be questioned about:

- Rating the accessibility to knowledge around (and related to the findings and results of) the COMPASS project (based on various dissemination activities)
- Rating the transparency of the dissemination activities

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- Rating the opportunity provided by the project to be involved in the COMPASS community, the interaction with them as stakeholders during the implementation phase, the feedback loops.
- Rating the opportunity provided by the COMPASS project for interaction with other end-users and exchange of knowledge.

From this feedback it will be possible to draw conclusions on the direct effects of the dissemination activities, although the real impact can only be evaluated in the longer term.

6.3. COMPASS Website traffic monitoring

To evaluate the success of our website, timeseries of metrics that provide insights into user acquisition, engagement, and behavior trends have been used. These metrics include monthly growth metrics and engagement metrics.

- **Growth Metrics**

Cumulative New Users: The total number of new users acquired up to each month. Tracking this on a month-to-month basis shows the growth trend of our user base.

Monthly New Users Growth Rate: Measures the month-over-month percentage increase in new users. This metric helps assess how quickly we are attracting new users. [Formula: $(NewUsersCurrentMonth - NewUsersPreviousMonth) / NewUsersPreviousMonth \times 100$].

- **Engagement Metrics**

User Retention Rate: The percentage of new users who return to the website after their first visit. [Formula: $(Users_who\ returned\ in\ the\ following\ month / NewUsers_in\ the\ base\ month) \times 100$]. This is crucial for understanding long-term engagement.

Engagement rate: The percentage of engaged session. An engaged session is defined as a session that lasted longer than 10 seconds, or had a conversion event, or had 2 or more screen or page views. Higher the engagement rates mean that the users found interesting content on the website that triggered them to stay longer and/or navigate through more than 2 pages.

Bounce rate: A bounce is a single-page session on the website. In Google Analytics, a bounce is calculated specifically as a session that triggers only a single request to the Analytics server, such as when a user opens a single page on the site and then exits without triggering any other requests to the Analytics server during that session.

Average Session Duration: The average duration (in seconds) of users' sessions. Higher durations usually denote an engaging content and/or user interest.

Table 1: COMPASS website metrics (up to date). Benchmark values are provided in the footnotes.

Website Metrics	Definition	Target Value
Users	The number of distinct active users who visited the COMPASS website. An active user is any user who has an engaged session or when Analytics	5,000

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Website Metrics	Definition	Target Value
	<i>collects the first visit event or engagement time msec parameter from a website</i>	
New users	<i>The number of users who interacted with your site or launched your app for the first time (event triggered: first_open)</i>	4,000
Returning users	<i>The number of unique users who initiated at least one previous session, regardless of whether or not the previous session was an engaged session, in the specified date range.</i>	500
Average engagement time	<i>Average engagement time per active user for the time period selected.</i>	> 1min
Sessions	<i>The number of sessions that began on the website</i>	5,000
New sessions rate	<i>Percentage of sessions that are generated by new users who have not previously visited the website (% new sessions: new users / total sessions)</i>	50 % ²
Average session duration	<i>The average duration (in seconds) of users' sessions</i>	> 2mins ³
Engaged sessions	<i>The number of sessions that lasted longer than 10 seconds, or had a conversion event, or had 2 or more screen or page views</i>	1,000
Engagement rate	<i>The percentage of engaged sessions (Engaged sessions divided by Sessions)</i>	≥ 50 % ⁴
Bounce rate	<i>The percentage of sessions that were not engaged sessions</i>	< 50% ⁵
Sessions per user	<i>The average number of sessions per user</i>	≥ 1.2
Engaged sessions per user	<i>The average number of engaged sessions per user</i>	≥ 0.5
Average engagement time per session	<i>The average engagement time (i.e. time that the COMPASS website was in focus in a user's browser) per session for active users</i>	≥ 30sec
Views	<i>The number of webpages the users saw. Repeated views of a single page are counted</i>	20,000
Views per session	<i>The number of webpages the users viewed per session. Repeated views of a single page are counted</i>	≥ 2 ⁶
Views per user	<i>The average number of webpages viewed per user</i>	≥ 2
Event count	<i>The number of times users triggered an event</i>	15,000
Events per session	<i>The average number of events per session</i>	≥ 4
Events per user	<i>The average number of events per user</i>	≥ 5

² A good site will have a healthy mix of new and returning site visitors, and this mix will vary depending on the site goals, business and industry. A range of 45% - 75% is often encountered (Source: <https://www.spinutech.com/digital-marketing/analytics/analysis/7-website-analytics-that-matter-most/>).

³ For a good average session duration, the industry standard is 2-3 minutes (Source: <https://www.spinutech.com/digital-marketing/analytics/analysis/7-website-analytics-that-matter-most/>). Average session duration benchmark values by industry type: engineering 3 mins, environmental services 2 mins 41 sec, software development 2 mins 38sec (Source: <https://firstpagesage.com/reports/average-session-duration-by-industry/>). Based on [Databox's Benchmark Groups - Google Analytics 4 Industry Benchmarks for 2023](#), the median average session duration was 2min 38sec

⁴ Based on [Databox's Benchmark Groups - Google Analytics 4 Industry Benchmarks for 2023](#), the median engagement rate across different industries was 56.23%

⁵ The average bounce rate ranges between 26% and 70% regardless of the industry (Source: <https://www.webfx.com/analytics/glossary/what-is-bounce-rate/>). According to [BusinessDIT](#), the average bounce rate regardless of industry is 55.43%. According to a study by Statista, the average bounce rate for websites is 47% (Source: <https://www.businessdit.com/bounce-rate-benchmarks/#source>). A bounce rate between 26% and 40% is considered very good (Source: <https://capturly.com/blog/average-bounce-rate-by-industry-2023-benchmark/>). Based on [Databox's Benchmark Groups - Google Analytics 4 Industry Benchmarks for 2023](#), the median bounce rate across different industries was 44.82%.

⁶ The unofficial industry standard is 2 pages per session (Source: <https://www.spinutech.com/digital-marketing/analytics/analysis/7-website-analytics-that-matter-most/>)

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Website Metrics	Definition	Target Value
First visits	<i>The number of times your users opened your website for the first time</i>	1,000
Event count: file_download	<i>The number of times users triggered the specific event “file_download” (public deliverable, project presentations, publications)</i>	300

7. Dissemination products' Quality and Standards

7.1. Corporate design, Identity

COMPASS has adopted a corporate identity which to the appearance and visibility of a project towards the outside. The benefit is a clear visibility, identification and association of the project with certain (positive) properties, transparency of its objectives, etc. Corporate behaviour in the framework of our project facilitates the development of the COMPASS into a quality label and makes it visible to the outside.

The following corporate elements have been developed (or are underway):

- Logo applications (in different colours and formats) for newsletters, brochures, reports, presentations, and other dissemination materials
- A ppt-template
- A Report template

All communication tools and materials (e.g. website, brochures, folders, reports, briefs etc.) are and will be developed according to the COMPASS Corporate Design. All partners will adhere to the given design and will use it for all applied dissemination activities. This corporate design creates a strong and clear image. As a consequence, target groups as well as the general public are less likely to forget the project.

Figure 6: The COMPASS logo

Figure 7: The COMPASS Powerpoint template

7.2. Quality control

To ensure that all dissemination products are of high quality some minimum standards have been set. The basic standard is to ensure and maximize the Quality, Objectivity, Utility, and Integrity of the information disseminated by the COMPASS. Objectivity involves both the presentation and substance. Objective presentation entails that the information is presented within a proper context to ensure an accurate, clear, complete, and unbiased presentation. Objective substance means that the data, the analytical process, and the resulting reports are accurate, reliable, and unbiased. The utility of information refers to its usefulness for the intended users. Integrity refers to the security of information, i.e. the protection of information from unauthorized access or revision. Integrity helps ensure that the information is not compromised through unauthorized revision, falsification, corruption, and intentional or inadvertent destruction.

The following guidelines have been set:

- Adopt the basic standard of quality (including objectivity, utility, and integrity) as a performance goal for all information that is disseminated.
- Review the quality of information before dissemination, with appropriate oversight by the Dissemination Officer. Internal peer will be used for that purpose, with at least 1 additional person involved as reviewer.
- Proper citation and referencing is always required. Since dissemination products may integrate news, posts, etc., originating for various sources, referencing rules are strict.
- Always seek up-to-date information that will trigger the target audience, as a general principle.
- Appearance should comply with the COMPASS corporate design.
- Allow and facilitate audiences' review: recipients may seek and obtain, where appropriate, timely correction of information maintained and disseminated. Their enquiry should be sent in via email.

7.3. Acknowledgements

All communication and dissemination products and activities of the beneficiaries related to the COMPASS action will acknowledge the funding received by EU Commission, will follow the publicity rules set by the

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Horizon Programme, and will be compliant with the relevant dissemination rules and guidelines. Additional acknowledgements, where applicable, should be clear and visible. The European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate) will be properly displayed, as presented below:

The following disclaimer should also be included in all COMPASS Deliverables.

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or of the European Health and Digital Executive Agency (HADEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority HADEA can be held responsible for them.

8. References

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https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf

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Website references:

[BusinessDIT](#)

[Databox's Benchmark Groups - Google Analytics 4 Industry Benchmarks for 2023](#)

[Databox's Benchmark Groups - Google Analytics 4 Industry Benchmarks for 2023](#)

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<https://capturly.com/blog/average-bounce-rate-by-industry-2023-benchmark/>

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ANNEX 1: Snapshots of the COMPASS website

News and Articles

compass-climate 0

Mozambique - Maputo Heavy Rains and Tropical Storm Filipo

12th March 2024, the Tropical Storm Filipo hit Gaza, Inhambane, Maputo and Sofala provinces, affecting 57,178 people (11,551 households) and...

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In the past years Europe has been hit by devastating extreme events. COMPASS will unravel the attribution of climate change to the changing impacts of those extremes. Hereto the project implements a climate attribution modelling framework that will be optimized with the learnings from a set of use-cases. I expect that the project will contribute to raising societal awareness by considering the complex interplay between multiple hazards and by also identifying the underlying socio-economic drivers of the impact severity.

—

Frederiek Sperna Weiland
DELTA RES

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COMPASS aims to develop novel methods to bridge the gap from attribution of univariate extremes to attribution of complex extremes, as well as from hazard-centred analysis to an impact-centred perspective. We will demonstrate the applicability of the COMPASS tools in a set of use cases, covering different regions and hazards, focusing on various compound extremes, including combinations of flooding and storms, heatwaves and drought, tropical cyclones. We aspire to lay the methodological foundation and an operational protocol, on which an operational service as part of the Copernicus Climate Change Services could be built.

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The COMPASS Consortium

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COMPASS has a strong focus on user engagement. By involving local stakeholders to help define relevant impact pathways and storylines of future vulnerability and exposure, we aim to increase our impact on the use cases and boost uptake of results. By presenting our work not only to the scientific audience, but also to practitioners, civil protection services and policy-makers we attempt to prove benefits for the larger society. To maximise our impact, a wide portfolio of dissemination and exploitation activities have been planned, tailored to the interest and level of expertise of each audience.

—

Maggie Kossida
SEVEN

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Our Data & Output

Download our project generated **Data**.

Browse through our open access project **Deliverables** to discover more.

Data

Output

Deliverable 7.1 – COMPASS Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of results including communication activities

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Our Use Cases

The COMPASS use cases provide a real-world testbed and insights in the feasibility of attributing compound extremes and their impacts to climate change.

COMPASS will develop a harmonised, yet flexible methodological framework that furnishes event-specific steps for the attribution of climate change as a driver of impacts in complex extremes. This framework will be validated and applied to a set of diverse use cases, that cover compound events, sequences of events and cascading events.

Our selected use cases cover complex extremes for various hazard types and impact contexts:

- France: compound flooding and storm during cyclone Xynthia in 2010
- United Kingdom: cluster of winter storms in 2013-2014 and drought combined with a heatwave in 2022
- Mozambique: compound flooding due to tropical cyclones Idai, Kenneth and Freddy in 2019 and 2023
- Caribbean: sequential tropical cyclones Eta and Iota in 2014
- Poland: single-country use case, not connected to a particular event, demonstrating an operational system for drought and heatwaves
- A second set of additional use cases will be defined during phase II of the project

France United Kingdom Mozambique

Caribbean Poland Phase II Use Cases

Facts and Figures: In the 2013-2014 the UK saw 13 major storms from December to mid-February, with the strength of the jet stream 30% above normal levels. This compound event resulted in severe coastal, river and groundwater flooding with more than 6,000 properties flooded. Strong winds that left 100,000 properties without power, also acted in combination with tidal surges and high tides to produce huge coastal waves. In 2022, the UK saw a different type of compound event with heatwaves in the summer leading to wildfires, drought, and high temperatures. The national temperature record was exceeded by 1.6°C, with a fourfold increase in wildfires compared to the year before, and the driest July on record since 1811 in England.

The COMPASS approach: Attribution of the compound flooding event will be done using a new high-resolution flood modeling attribution methods developed within COMPASS, with a focus on weather types/large-scale drivers.

Cyclone Dirk, United Kingdom
Date: 23/12/2013
Credit: NASA Worldview, MODIS imagery
[Source](#)

York floods, United Kingdom
Credit: Met Office
[Source](#)

News

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This image was captured by the SEVIRI instrument onboard the Meteosat-9 weather satellite, which is located at 45.5°E over the Indian Ocean.
Source: EUMETSAT, <https://www.eumetsat.int/image-week/tropicalstorm-filipo>

Mozambique – Maputo Heavy Rains and Tropical Storm Filipo

compass-climate April 16, 2024 No Comments

12th March 2024, the Tropical Storm Filipo hit Gaza, Inhambane, Maputo and Sofala provinces, affecting 57,178 people (11,551 households) and two casualties and injuring 85. Damage to infrastructure includes 1,674 houses partially damaged and 456 totally destroyed, 287 schools impacting 59,629 students, along with 75 health centres, 126 electric poles, and 256 km of road affected. Additionally, about 30,857 ha of crops were affected. (OCHA, 4 Apr 2024)

Between 23 and 24 March, heavy rains (100mm to 300mm) fell on Maputo city and Maputo province, affecting a total of 96,239 people (20,215 families), with nine deaths and seven injured, according to the National Institute for Disaster Management (INGD). The rains also damaged public and private infrastructure and impacted road access to Matola and Maputo provinces. A total of 173 houses were partially damaged, 99 totally destroyed and 20,023, flooded. At least 61 schools were affected, corresponding to 113 classrooms and 78,727 students and 807 teachers. About 13,584 ha of crops were also affected, as well as 275 km of roads damaged.

For more information read the UN Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) Flash Update No. 4 [here](#).

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 Mozambique - Maputo Heavy Rains and Tropical Storm Filipo
April 16, 2024

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